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*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

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Project Handbook**

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FINAL VERSION

4.0	25.05.2023	Stella (VUB)	Arapoglou	Format review, version ready for submission
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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract | This deliverable provides a summarised description of the necessary structures for the overall management of the WIMBY project, encompassing the internal guidelines for communication and working procedures for decision-making as well as risk management procedures.

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LIST OF PARTNERS

No	Logo	Name	Short Name	Country
1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU	Denmark
3		INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	IIASA	Austria
4		UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	Austria
5		UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
6		NAZKA MAPPS BVBA	NAZKA	Belgium
7		KELSO INSTITUTE EUROPE GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	KIE	Germany
8		DEEP BLUE SRL	DEEP BLUE	Italy
9		UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU	Netherlands
10		POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	Italy
11		UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO	UNIPA	Italy
12		APREN-ASSOCIACAO PORTUGUESA DE ENERGIAS RENOVAVEIS	APREN	Portugal
13		MULTICONSULT NORGE AS	MCN	Norway
14		EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	ETH Zürich	Switzerland
15		PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	PSI	Switzerland
16		UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UCL	United Kingdom

ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
DoW	Description of Work
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
GA	Grant Agreement

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides a summarised description of the necessary structures for the overall management of the WIMBY project, encompassing the internal guidelines for communication and working procedures for decision-making. This report aims to provide clear internal communication guidelines to ensure maximum efficiency and productivity. The deliverable also addresses the risk management plans and includes definitions and details of the processes being implemented with respect to the WIMBY project. This deliverable is a living document that will be revised if necessary (e.g. General Assembly, Executive Board meetings).

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations:

This deliverable is related to task 7.1 Project Coordination and operational management lead by VUB. All objectives were achieved without deviation of content nor time.

1. GOVERNANCE

1.1 Governance structure

Figure 1. WIMBY project governance structure

1.1.1 The European Commission

The European Commission (EC) is represented by the European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA): they have the role of the Contractor and are represented by the Project Officer.

1.1.2 The General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is made up by representatives of all Partners. The GA acts as the highest conflict resolution body within the project.

Main responsibilities: approval of reports, resource allocation on project level, monitoring of overall progress implementation, strategic project orientation.

The GA meets at least once a year onsite (if possible); a second (online) meeting is highly recommended, to ensure proper progress monitoring. Extraordinary meetings will be organized after specific requests have been submitted to the Coordinator or to the Executive Board (EB).

The meetings will be organized by the Coordinator and the hosting Partner (s):

- The Coordinator is in charge of sending out invitations, preparing the agenda, gathering presentations and drafting minutes.
- The hosting Partner(s) is/are in charge of the logistics and drafting minutes.

1.1.3 *The Executive Board (EB)*

The EB is made up by representatives of the WP Leaders: they meet on a bi-monthly basis in order

- to monitor progress implementation on WP and Task level
- to monitor issues before they are escalated into risks
- to monitor the status of deliverables and milestones
- to provide administrative updates, if any

The EB is the highest decision-making body of the project, as instructed by the Consortium Agreement. All Partners will be invited to attend the meetings every 4 months.

The meetings will be organized by the Coordinator, who is in charge of sending out invitations, developing the agenda, gathering content and input and drafting minutes. All WP leaders are required to contribute with content (agenda and presentations).

A dedicated day was agreed at the Kick-off Meeting (every 2 months on the first Tuesday of the Month at 10:30-12:00 CET), to ensure all WP leaders are available to attend all meetings.

1.1.4 *Cross-cutting issues*

Data Protection Management & Ethics management

All data privacy and ethics issues will be managed according to the provisions made in Chapter 4. Ethics self-assessment of the Grant Agreement.

VUB will provide sufficient expertise and support (DPO, R&D Legal Office).

Gender balance management

The Consortium of WIMBY is determined to work against all types of discrimination, while introducing a multi-dimensional gender balance management:

- In decision making: the EB, consisting of the WP Leaders, is and will remain fully gender balanced (50% female representation).
- In project implementation: all Partners ensure equal employment opportunities for project personnel.

- In communication and dissemination: all material is and will be gender inclusive.
- In target audiences: people will never be excluded or discriminated against based on their gender identity. Targeted audiences will be identified and contacted, to achieve the highest gender balance (invited keynote speakers, external experts and stakeholder representatives).
- Gender sensitive analysis: whenever possible gender segregation of data and a focus on other socially vulnerable groups will be undertaken. Gender perspective alternatives will be provided. The Consortium will be incentivized to join EuroGender, the European Institute for Gender Equality's online cooperation and consultation hub and participate in gender equality training courses, online discussions and surveys.
- Policy recommendations: dedicated suggestions and guidelines towards gender balanced participation and focus on enhancing the active role of female citizens will be developed.

1.1.5 The Advisory Board (AB)

According to the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA, article 6.6), the Advisory Board will be appointed and steered by the General Assembly. The Project Coordinator will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all Parties and each AB member. The Scientific Coordinator shall write the minutes of the AB meetings and submit them to the General Assembly. The AB members shall be allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights.

The objectives of the AB are

- to guide the Consortium towards the achievement of the project objectives
- to support the dissemination activities and participate in open access publications

The first potential members of AB, who have already signed a Letter of Intent are: ENGIE, Renewable Energy BeLux, Siemens, Gamesa Renewable Energy, EDP renewables S.A., Greek Public Power Corporation S.A., Greenventory GmbH, TwingTec, Postdam Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, European Renewable Energies Federation, Canada Research Chair in Urban

Planning for Climate Change, Finerge S.A., EDA Renováveis, S.A., Ventient Energy.

The overall responsibility of the AB falls under the Scientific Coordinator of the project.

1.1.6 Conflict resolution

Any issues will be resolved within the Consortium before they are escalated into risks. Regarding conflicts, the resolution will be carried out in order of authority:

1. WP level: the WP leader in cooperation with the task Partners will attempt to resolve any conflicts, before they escalate.
2. Project level: if a specific conflict is not resolved on WP level, it will be escalated to the EB.
3. If necessary, the issue will be directed to the GA (the highest conflict resolution body). The GA can organize a conflict resolution dedicated meeting, following a written request of the party/parties involved.
4. If consensus cannot be reached, the matter is to be resolved by vote of the partners' representatives (one vote per partner). The approval of a decision will require a majority vote.
5. The EC will be notified and informed regarding the nature of the risk and mitigation. If required, there will be a request for guidance and advice towards the EC. This will ensure that the decided solution and mitigation will abide by all rules and regulations.

The conflict resolution procedures do not apply in cases where the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement can already provide solutions.

2. PROGRESS REPORTING

2.1 Financial interim report

Every six months, using the tools provided by the Coordinator (excel files), all Partners are obliged to provide a report on Person-Months (PM) and direct costs spent during the interim period as per the schedule below:

Table 1. Schedule of financial interim report and deadlines

Interim report	Reporting period	Deadline
1st interim report	January 2023 (M01) – June 2023 (M06)	July 2023
2nd interim report	July 2023 (M07) – December 2023 (M12)	January 2024
3rd interim report	January 2024 (M13) – June 2024 (M18) OFFICIAL PR1 (M01-M18)	July 2024 August 2024
4th interim report	July 2024 (M19) – December 2024 (M24)	January 2025
5th interim report	January 2025 (M25) – June 2025 (M30)	July 2025
	OFFICIAL FINAL REPORT (M19-M36)	February 2026

2.2 Periodic and Final reporting

The Coordinator is responsible for the preparation and submission of the report to the European Commission. The organization of the review meeting also falls under the Coordinator's responsibility.

Each WP leader is responsible for providing input and information on the project progress on WP level (status, contribution, challenges, risks) within 4 weeks after the end of the reporting period.

Each partner is responsible for providing their financial data and input for the continuous reporting within 4 weeks after the end of each reporting period.

The reporting periods of the project are:

RP01: January 2023–June 2024 Periodic Report

RP02: July 2024–December 2025 Final Report

3. CHANGE MANAGEMENT

The following changes always require an amendment:

- changes to the description of the action in Annex 1
- changes to the budget category for volunteers (if used)
- changes to budget categories with lump sums costs or contributions (if used; including financing not linked to costs)
- changes to budget categories or activities with higher funding rates or budget ceilings (if used).
- activation of the contingency reserve (where foreseen in the grant agreement)

The following require either an amendment or a simplified approval procedure:

- addition of amounts for subcontracts not provided for in Annex 1
- other changes in certain specific cost categories, if specifically provided for in Article 6.2.

Approval of an amendment is at the full discretion of the Commission/Agency and there is no automatic entitlement to it. Beneficiaries that rely on the simplified approval procedure, bear the full risk of non-approval and rejection of costs by the Commission/Agency.

4. QUALITY MANAGEMENT

4.1 Review of project deliverables

Partners are responsible for the development and preparation of the deliverables. The Coordinator is responsible to ensure that all deliverables will go through a quality review process and will be submitted on time (contractual submission dates, according to GA).

The procedure that will be followed to ensure on time submission according to quality criteria is:

Step 1: Partner in charge of deliverable sends the first consolidated version to the reviewers (according to the list of reviewers on the project SharePoint) 3 weeks before contractual submission date. The Coordinator is always In CC.

Step 2: The reviewers have 5 working days to complete the review of the document. They send back the reviewed version of the deliverable to the partner in charge of the deliverable. The Coordinator remains in cc.

Step 3: The Partner responsible has 5 working days to integrate suggestions and respond to comments made by the reviewers. This final version is sent to the Coordinator.

Step 4: The Coordinator has 5 working days to review the document (format, deliverable information, executive summary, cross references, working links etc).

Step 5: The final, reviewed version is submitted by the Coordinator.

Figure 2. Timeline of deliverable's review process

Quality criteria of deliverables:

- reflect the work and results
- be relevant, simple, readable

Format and other criteria of deliverables:

- contain an executive summary
- working links and cross references
- typos, etc
- logos, contractual information

4.2 *Templates*

The Communication Manager in cooperation with the Coordinator will develop templates (word, PowerPoint, deliverables, etc), to ensure standardized procedures. All templates will be kept on the project repository.

5. RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk Management Plan:

- **Risk identification:**

Includes risks identified during proposal stage. Unidentified risks will be monitored through the risk log; it will be created in the beginning of the project and will be updated during each EB meeting.

- **Risk Analysis, Evaluation and Resolution**

With every addition to the risk log, a mitigation response will be provided by the responsible partner. Also, the likelihood and severity will be recognised for each additional risk.

- **Risk monitoring**

The owner of the risk is responsible of monitoring and reporting on the issue monthly (at the EB meeting).

6. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

6.1 Project contact list

The Coordinator is responsible of keeping the project contact list up to date, with the contribution of the partners. The list (all versions) is kept on the project repository.

Mailing lists were created and manned by the communication manager to ease the communications within the Consortium:

- CONSORTIUM@wimby.eu (full Consortium)
- GA@wimby.eu (General Assembly - all the main contacts from each partner)
- EB@wimby.eu (members of the EB group)
- FINANCES@wimby.be (all admin and finances contacts)

6.2 Meetings

Project management meetings (namely GA and EB) are described in Chapter 1.1. In addition to those, regular technical meetings at WP level will be organized online (and onsite if necessary). Technical meetings will be organized and documented under the responsibility of the Partner organizing the meeting, typically the WP or Task leader.

6.3 Repository/ record keeping

The project repository is hosted on the VUB SharePoint: a dedicated space has been set up with access restricted to the Consortium and VUB IT Department.

The SharePoint will be managed and stay updated by the Coordinator (who is owner). Access rights will be granted to new team members.

6.4 Main communication channels

Main communication channel is electronic mail; all Partners are required to respect deadlines and to respond within the suggested time. In case a Partner remains unresponsive to electronic mail, the coordinator will contact through other channels (phone, Mattermost, MS Teams, post). If the partner remains unresponsive, the issue will be escalated to risk and will be discussed in the following EB.

In order to ease the day-to-day communication, the GA decided to use a dedicated platform for instant messaging. This will minimize the hoarding of

electronic emails and will allow easy and flexible interactions among partners.

After researching the market, the GA decided to use [Mattermost](#), which offers effective real-time communication, file and code snippet sharing, in-line code syntax highlighting, and workflow automation purpose-built for technical teams. A specific structure will be created to allow project teams (on WP, Task and topic level) to work efficiently together. The Project Coordinator, with the support of the communication leader (DBL), is responsible for the management of the platform and costs related to it.

7. SUPPORTING DOCUMENTS

7.1 Horizon Europe documents

Horizon Europe [Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#) (AMGA) is a user guide explaining all articles of the Grant Agreement, providing examples and sample calculations.

Horizon Europe [Online Manual](#): It is an online user guide for EU funding and managing projects. Provides detailed information and step-by-step guides on keeping records, amendments, reports & payment requests, deliverables & milestones, dissemination & exploitation, communicating your project, acknowledgement of EU funding and checks, audits, reviews & investigations.

Horizon Europe [Reference Documents](#): This page includes reference documents of the programmes managed on the EU Funding & Tenders portal starting with legal documents and the Commission work programmes up to model grant agreements and guides for specific actions.

Horizon Europe [Reporting Template](#): The template provides detailed instructions on project's periodic and final reporting.

REFERENCES

WIMBY Grant Agreement No. 101083460

WIMBY Consortium Agreement

AGA–Annotated Model Grant Agreement EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

